

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VIII, August 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

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World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.179-180 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

OLD WOUNDS

Alfie Maria R. Custodio, PhD.

Dean, Business College, NDDU

Gen. Santos City, Region 12, Philippines

The Philippines, aspiring to be an upper middle-income country, still grapples with the complexities of poverty amidst a changing climate. While progress has been made in poverty reduction, the country continues to face significant challenges, both in urban and rural areas. The overarching goal of eradicating extreme poverty by 2030, as outlined in the Sustainable Development Goals, remains elusive.

Climate change, as with other countries has emerged as a formidable threat, exacerbating poverty and inequality. The Philippines, already facing a lot of natural disasters and environmental degradation is now also experiencing extreme weather events, and they not only disrupt lives but also erode development gains. The rising sea levels and saltwater intrusion threaten coastal communities, agriculture, and fisheries, undermining food security and livelihoods. To address these intertwined crises, a comprehensive approach is needed that integrates climate resilience into poverty reduction strategies. This involves investing in early warning systems, disaster preparedness, and climate-smart agriculture while promoting renewable energy and sustainable livelihoods.

Poverty, our old wound, exacerbated by inequalities in income and opportunities, persists as a pressing issue. Addressing this requires a multifaceted approach that considers urban and rural development, agricultural productivity, and access to basic services. To accelerate progress, it is essential to monitor the impact of programs on vulnerable households, ensuring they are protected from both poverty and climate-related risks. Disaster preparedness and response are critical components of poverty reduction. Real-time data, life-saving aid, and livelihood support are essential for building resilience. Gender equality is also a crucial factor, as women are disproportionately affected by poverty and climate change. Empowering women through economic opportunities and political participation is essential for sustainable development.

Given the persistent challenges of poverty and inequality, what specific, measurable targets and timelines have been set by both national and local governments to significantly reduce poverty rates in both urban and rural areas? How will each administration ensure that social protection programs are effectively targeted to the most vulnerable populations, particularly those affected by both poverty and climate change? What strategies were implemented to empower women and marginalized groups to participate fully in the economy and decision-making processes, thereby contributing to poverty reduction and gender equality? How did the different sectors invest in building the resilience of communities to climate-related disasters, ensuring that poverty reduction efforts are sustainable in the long term? What specific measures have been taken so far to improve data collection and analysis on poverty and inequality to inform evidence-based policymaking and program implementation?

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Sadly, these questions are repeated over and over and most have only given birth to further questions. Let us go back perhaps to hoping and asking for active citizenship and participation as they are vital too for driving positive change. Marginalized groups, including women and youth, must have a voice in decision-making processes that affect their lives. Sharing best practices and assessing policy implementation is essential for continuous improvement. While the country has made strides, the challenges of poverty and climate change persist. To achieve lasting progress, strategies must focus on both short-term relief and long-term sustainability. A robust database is crucial for effective program implementation, monitoring, and evaluation. The long-term impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic has further compounded these challenges. By addressing the interconnected issues of poverty and climate change, the Philippines can build a more resilient and equitable future for all its citizens. Again, good luck!

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13353051

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